

ISic0042

I.Sicily inscription 0042

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

architrave

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Segesta

Place of origin (modern)

Segesta

Provenance

Found in the ruins of ancient Segesta (without further detail recorded)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas,
inventory 3543

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 25 cm

Width 97 cm

Depth 20 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 120 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: NA mm

Text

1. [---][dei]vi · f(ilio) · deivo · L(ucius) · Sem[pronius][---]

Apparatus

Text compared against photograph, as per ILPalermo and ISegesta

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491765

EDCS 22000849

Bibliography

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